

THE STUDENT EXPERIENCE IN HIGH EDUCATION BEYOND BRANDING: A CASE STUDY IN LIMKOKWING UNIVERSITY OF CREATIVE TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: Over the time. Education beyond branding of student experience, the student experience in high education beyond branding. Education beyond branding in high university in Malaysia, the study used a sample of 100 populations, 100 for the student in Limkokwing University of Creative Technology. The total simple size was 100 populations as a part of this research and the statistical package for social science (spss) was used to carry out the analysis. Data were analyzed using the regression of the correlation to own the t-test hypotheses. The findings of the study showed that there exist a positive relationship between the student and their experience in the university. It was recommended that students be aided to develop effective study experience, so as to be successful in the education academic.

Keywords: high education, student experience, education academic.

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

This research is on factors influencing student experience in higher education.

This is important because organization branding through student experience is more effective beyond the branding that is being put forward by the learning institution itself, especially for the purpose attracting potential students to study at the learning institution. The focus of this study is the students in Malaysia. However it may apply to other learning institutions in general.

1.1 Background of the study

Experience in higher education beyond branding is required as the increasing liberalization of higher education has caused changes in the way the student experiences are supported. In the field of education, learning has been discovered all over the world to be a highly complex problem. Several researchers have tried to explain it differently and the description of each is partially true. Over the years, researches on factors that influence experience in high education beyond branding of students have attracted the interest of not only researchers but concern of teachers, and school administrators as well. Study

method is the knowledge and application of effective study skills or techniques by students. In 1995, the then Prime Minister, Tun Dr. Mahathir Mohammad and a delegation from Malaysia made a working visit to Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and endorsed the establishment of a university modelled after MIT. An agreement was signed in January 1997 to establish the Limkokwing University of Creative Technology (MUST).

In order to remain modest, it has become common practice for higher education providers to employ service quality and excellence in the management framework to evaluate and improve facility delivery and service encounters for its students. This is particularly true in higher education where employees need specialist skills to deliver a wide range of face-to-face services (Matlay, 2005, 2006). This may be due to such organizations having implemented service excellence for a longer period of time. It should be noted that the organizations surveyed were at different implementation stages of their service excellence plans and the respondents felt that they would need to refer to internal records and employee opinion surveys as well as surveys of external clients in order to accurately measure service excellence.

The respondents also mentioned their personal values as a means of sustaining and improving service excellence at their workplace. In order to achieve service excellence in higher education, the key intervention areas suggested by Gilthorpe (2006) should be addressed, including recruitment, induction, training, caring, support, reward, recognition, listening to customers and management spending time making processes more interesting. Research suggests that these processes could be adopted in higher education institutions (HEIs) by involving most, if not all, employees within an institution (Oakland, 2001). The resulting equity model is then tested in an emerging market using both current and prospective higher education (HE) students. HE provides an interesting and important context for the research, since HEI across the world have become increasingly 'market oriented' and students increasingly become 'consumers' (Chen, 2008; Mazzarol and Soutar, 2008). The cultural perspective concerns with the way an organization aligns its vision, culture, and image with the brand identity (Hatch and Schultz, 2001). The behavioral perspective, on the other hand, focuses on the importance given to 'living the brand', which is manifested in the organization's integrated marketing communication, brand equity measurement, corporate identity, corporate design, and the effect of branding on management practice (Urde et al., 2011).

1.2 Problem Statement

Due to the intensified competition with the sector, higher education institutions are becoming more customer-oriented and resort to the implementation of integrated marketing approaches to attract enrolments. Brand problem challenges to the rebranding of MUST as a blended learning university which gains international recognition as reputable university. It was noted that many universities adopt a brand management strategy in order to improve their ranking in the HE market (Brunzel, 2007). Student learning experiences are a problem as they remain as a challenge to enhance the learning experience of the students in a creative learning and blended learning environment. The marketing problem promotes student learning experience as marketing advantages and competitive strategy for the success of marketing. In an abstract sense, brand equity provides marketers with a strategic bridge from their past to their future (Keller, 2003). Value creation and university direction problem to create new value and new direction for university, which is blended learning and students experiences as new core values and new direction towards university success. The problem is, however, that there is little known so far how those global changes have translated into student's experiences. Studies report, for example, that as a consequence of neoliberal market drivers, a more individualized experience is fostered by organizations, and in doing so, highlights the need to understand affective states and emotions in student experiences (Jeleniewski Seidler, 2012). Hence, this study focuses on the students' perception of a university's brand orientation and thus focuses on the behavioral perspective of brand orientation within the higher education sector.

1.3 Research Objectives

The main objective of this research is to study the student experience in higher education beyond branding.

1. To examine the effectiveness of pre - enrolment of students towards student experience.
2. To analyse the degree of active students engagement toward students experience.
3. Employability perception and satisfaction

1.4 Research Questions

The following are the research questions of this study:-

1. How effective of pre - enrolment of students towards student experience?
2. What are the success factors of active student's engagement toward student's experience?
3. What is the Employability perception and satisfaction?

1.5 Thesis Structure

This research will be presented in five chapters, and will build the discussion and analysis through the following chapters as follows. Chapter 1 will reveal the introductory part of the project, background of the study, statement of the problem, research objectives, and questions. Chapter 2 will present the scholarly review of the literature on subject matter, and it is followed by chapter 3, which presents methodology of the research design, sample and proposed data methods. Chapter 4 will entail on the findings of the investigation, this will be based on the investigation findings together with analysis and chapter 5 will showcase the outcome of the study together with conclusion, commendations and future enhancement.

1.6 Scope of the Study

This study will carry out its research in Limkokwing University of Creative Technology to investigate and examine the student experience in higher education and it will be studied in context as to how student experiences are more important than branding.

1.7 Significance of the study

There are not many researches that have examined the effects of students experience in the HE sector, particularly, the other factors besides the branding of the HEI. This research however focuses on the determinants of the students experiences that made them to be part of the learning institution.

This research will provide better understanding on the acceptance of the student's experience which contributes to the liking of the students toward the HEI and not because of the branding. The better understanding of this factor in HEIs will be beneficial to the stakeholders. This research also seeks to provide more informative data on how to improve and enhance their strategies in order to compete more effectively with other well established and known HEI in Malaysia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the theoretical work of the research and review the student experience in higher education and branding. In addition, this chapter also investigates and examines the factors affecting student experience beyond branding in higher education.

2.2 The Student Experience

The student experience in today's complex and highly competitive marketplace, universities and colleges have turned to branding as a solution in dealing with today's global challenges (Whisman, 2007). Given the growing importance of branding for the competitiveness of higher education in the global economy, this paper presents a framework to help better understand and guide branding decisions for college and universities. In this regard, it is suggested that a brand ecosystem framework (Pinar and Trapp, 2008) refer to student experiences both within and outside the classroom (Douglas et al., 2008; Voss, 2009; Yeo, 2009), and the applicability of commercial branding in higher education settings (Jevons, 2006).

2.3 Education Branding

Education or university branding is a heightens that need to be in every institutions to understand, manage and leverage a strong brand position for the school. A university brand represents the totality of perceptions and feelings that stakeholders associate with that particular university (Ali-Choudhury, Bennett, & Savani, 2009; Batra, Ahuvia, & Baggozzi, 2012). For

any organization, a brand constitutes a valuable asset when managed in a holistic, integrative manner that builds long-term brand health (Mirzaei, Gray, Baumann, Johnson & Winzar 2015). According to Hemsley-Brown and Goonawardana, as a result, in 2000, the UK government supported a worldwide re-branding exercise campaign to establish a clear and competitive identity for UK universities in order to attract more international student. A deep understanding of consumer perceptions of social media activities by brand managers is crucial for consumer engagement and trust of the brand, according to Gensler et al., 2012; social media is a key component of the marketing mix, affecting the relationship between consumers and brands.

2.4 Student Relationship

The relationships that teachers develop with their students play an important role in the academic growth of the student. According to Hallinan (2008), learning is a process that involves cognitive, social and psychological dimensions, and both processes should be considered if academic achievement is to be maximized. Their results provide support for further study by the inclusion of interpersonal relationships in the instructional setting and to what degree those relationships affect the students' learning environment. The quality of the relationship between a student and the teacher will result in a greater degree of learning in the classroom Downey (2008). According to Hamre and Pianta (2006), on their investigation of the importance of teacher-student relationships, it was revealed that aggressive teacher behavior is perceived by students as not only affecting their ability to focus on their schoolwork, but also to be instrumental in damaging their relationships with teachers (Lewis et al., 2012).

2.5 Pre- Enrollment

These studies have tended to find negative responses to premiums, to the best of my knowledge; no studies have yet considered the effects of premiums on the length of adult enrollment, Chandra et al. (2010, 2012). The use of exclusionary discipline in schools continues to increase, especially for African American students (Losen and Skiba, 2010). This held true particularly for out-of-school suspension, the use of the procedure is not restricted to serious or dangerous behavior, but rather appears to be most commonly used for more interactive day-to-day disruptions, especially defiance and noncompliance (Gregory & Weinstein, 2008; Skiba Horner, Chung, Rausch, May & Tobin 2011).

2.6 Active Student

When these positive student behaviors increase, it is less likely that students will have time to engage in inappropriate behaviors (Armendariz & Umbreit, 1999; Simonsen, Myers, & Deluca, 2010). These studies indicate that, when teachers provide a high rate of opportunities for students to respond during instruction, the likelihood that student will be engaged is increased (Hattie, 2012; Rosenshine & Berliner, 1978). According to Velasquez (2011) explained that the students those who used active listening techniques to stay engaged in a class lecture demonstrated better marks on exams and the report described the various strategies that successful students use to mentally participate in the learning process.

2.7 Employability and Satisfaction

It is recognized that that the impact of perceived job insecurity on well-being varies both among individuals (Sverke and Hellgren, 2002), and across socio-economic categories, though there are few firmly established regularities across many studies (Nolan et al., 2000). According to Robinson (2000) has a different opinion, she believes that employability skills are teachable skills and may be taught in employability skills. Furthermore, she suggests that instructions should be designed to ensure goals and objectives are attainable. Zinser (2003) shares view. He believes that career and employability skills should be taught in schools, since many students leave education without the requisite skills to succeed in the adult work world. According to Poon (2014) suggested that emotional intelligence should not observe directly. Although the importance of emotional intelligence has observed as moderator in the several setting such as i.e, the moderating variability of emotional intelligence between the several variables, i.e., Ciarrochi, Deane & Anderson (2002) suggested that emotional intelligence has significant and positive role in the stress and mental health.

2.8 Theoretical Framework

2.9 Hypothesis

The following will be the hypotheses for the study:

- H1. Student perception of the pre enrolment has a positive impact on student experience.
- H2. Student active engagement at the university has a positive impact on student post- enrolment communication beh

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter will be giving experimental proof and speaking about the student experience in higher education beyond branding, it will likewise utilize suitable research strategies and methods in analyzing the research premises before reaching a conclusion. It will likewise give more subtle elements on the approach of research. Sampling methods, data accumulation instruments, research populace and test size, statistical part utilized in the study and limitation of the investigation, pilot test. Besides, the research standards will likewise be expressed in the chapter.

3.1 Selection of IVs

This study employed quantitative methodology which seeks to ascertain the factors affecting student experience beyond branding in higher education. A sample population will be used to collect the primary data using the structured questionnaire as the research instrument. The independent variable is the condition that changeable in a study. My independent variable for this study is focusing on pre-enrollment of student, active student, and employability perception and satisfaction of student toward student experience

3.2 Method of study

This method will be using the questionnaire method, to know the number of student and teachers in high universities. While some researchers have proposed survey instruments for the assessment of the quality of student experiences, some limitations exist (Tam, 2006, 2007, Webber et al., 2013).

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3.3 Hypotheses

The following will be the hypotheses for the study:

- H1.** Student perception of the pre-enrolment has a positive impact on student experience.
- H2.** Student active engagement at the university has a positive impact on student experience.
- H3.** Student employability perception and satisfaction has a positive impact on student experience.

3.4 Population of the study

The target population for this study consists of students in Limkokwing University of Creative Technology. The population of the study will 100 between the students. The research populace indicates to a group that have some basic component where the finding of the will be applied Weathington, Pittenger, Cunningham (2012). The research will have a vast study sample response for the staff not withstanding his or her academic background

3.5 Sampling method

Random sampling technique was used in this research. This is a sample technique which is certainly not a non-probability sampling method where subjects are selected because of their convenient accessibility and more likely the availability to the researcher. This technique is sensible since it will ensure that all participants of the populace get an indistinguishable right to share in the research sampling. Data gathering tools will be utilized to gather representations being considered.

3.6 Research instrument

The instrument used for the collection of data for the purpose of this research was a questionnaire. The good point Liker scale was used in structuring the questionnaire. The questionnaire also had sections: A, B, C, D, E, and F. The report will choice from the following question, strongly disagree (SD), Disagree (D), neither agree nor disagree (ND), Agree (A) and strongly agree (SA). The questionnaires are in 7 sections namely A, B, C, D, E, and F which is as follow. Section A contained the demographic detail or personal data of the students. Section B contained pre enrollment for the student. Section C contains Active student engagement for the student. Section D contains employability and satisfaction for the student. Section E contains student experience for the student and section F contains perception on branding for the student

3.7 Validation of the Instrument

To ensure the content and face validity of the instrument, the draft copy of the questionnaire was given to the project supervisor for validation. Based on the supervisor's corrections, the final draft was prepared and used for data collection.

3.8 Statistical methods

The research data handled in this research are produced with the questionnaires issued. The statistical analysis adopted was a correlation, the statistical instrument is use to determine the present statistical significant affiliation concerning the dependent and independent variables. According to Kothari (2004). Correlation analysis is the relationship between two properties or the amount of measuring the extent to which the interdependence of the variable quantities.

All computations requiring the use of data analysis technique were accessed by a computer statistical software package called SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

3.9 Research Limitations

These are some limitations in this research work. In the sense that the student relationship in education will be considered here as the influence of the study. In some other higher education branding in the teachers, lecturers, and the president of the university.

4. DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data obtained from the survey. The aim of the research is to examine the effectiveness of pre-enrolment, active student engagement, employability and satisfaction of students towards student experience in university. The research uses a primary survey method in gathering data through questionnaires, the outcome of this chapter will help to test the hypotheses.

4.1 Analysis of Data Reliability

The Cronbach’s coefficient alpha was analyzed as a specialized test to see the consistency of survey item. According to pallant (2010) the acceptable value of Cronbach’s alpha has to be more than 0.70 for the internal consistency of survey data. In this study, almost some of the construct was found to be reliable, and the researcher found that the survey data is appropriate enough for the test of hypothesis. The Cronbach’s alphas through spss suggest that the survey data is reliable on overall base. The reliability test was run on the data using spss and there were 100 valid samples for the study. There were no missing values and hence no samples were excluded from the test. The results of the cronbach alpha test revealed that the alpha value was 0.830. this value indicates that all the variables were reliable and their internal consistency was high and the instrument is reliable.

Table 4.1: Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	100	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	100	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.830	25

This shows the measures in the study research, validity test is also essential. Validity and uni-dimensionality of measures of some of the variable under study. The factor analysis is required to assess the validity of the construct, whether it is according to proposed variables as have been earlier theorized in the research framework.

4.2 Profile of Respondents

Table 4.2 shows the results of the gender respondents are presented. It is seen that most of the respondent are male constituting 60.0% while the female constitute 39.0% of total respondents sampled. The total respondent of all is 100.0%. In the result of age respondent, the percent of 18 is 6.9% percent and the valid percent is 9.0%. The respondent of 18-25 in percent is 57.7% percent, the valid percent is 75.0% percent and cumulative percent is 84.0% percent and the respondent of 25 in percent is 10.8% percent, the valid percent is 14.0% percent and the cumulative of 18-25 and 25 is 99.0% percent

This is the program level of respondent of the student in Limkokwing University of Creative Technology, the program level foundation percent is 24.0% percent, the valid percent is 24.0% percent and the cumulative percent is 24.0% percent. The diploma percent is 47.0% percent, the valid percent is 47.0% percent and the cumulative percent is 71.0% percent. The bachelor percent is 22.0% percent, the valid 22.0% percent and the cumulative percent is 93.0% percent. The master’s percent is 2.0% percent, the valid percent is 2.0% percent and the cumulative percent is 95.0%. In the PhD percent is 5.0% percent, the valid percent is 5.0% percent and the cumulative is 100.0% percent.

Table 4.2 Profile Respondent

Demographic attributes		Number of responses	Cumulative Percentage
		60	60.0%
Age	<18	39	99.0%
	18- 25	9	9.0%
	>25	14	84.0%
			98.0%
Program	Business	24	24.0%
	IT	6	30.0%
	Biotechnonology	8	38.0%
	Telco	8	46.0%
	Transportation &Logistics	54	100.0%

Program Level	Foundation	24	24.0%
	Diploma	47	71.0%
	Bachelor	22	93.0%
	Master	2	95.0%
	Ph.D.	5	100.0%
Nationality	Local	71	71.0%
	Foreigner	26	97.0%

4.3 Descriptive analysis

The analysis of survey response is done presented in this section. Mean and standard deviation are the principle test in this section. The mean analysis refer to measure of central tendency and deviation around mean is referred through analysis of standard deviation. According to pallant (2010) approximately 1 can be standard acceptable value of standard deviation. Table 4.3.1 presents of the results of descriptive analysis for the responses of the questionnaire which were measured using a 5-point likert scale. The variables B1-B5 indicates the factors related with the pre-enrollment, C1-C5 relate about the active student engagement, D1-D5 specify the aspect related to employability and satisfaction, E1-E5 stated about the student experience and F1-F5 deals with the perception on branding

Table 4.4.1: Correlation between Pre-Enrollment

		Pre Enrollment	B5
Pre Enrollment	Pearson Correlation	1	.271**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006
	N	100	100
B5	Pearson Correlation	.271**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This correlation shows the relationship between student perception of the pre-enrollment has a positive impact on student. It yields a positive correlation coefficient (N) =100 it shows that there is exist a positive significant relationship between this two variables and a returned p-value of 0.006. These indicate the relationship significant is good since p-value is 0.006 (level of significant). Hence, we accept H1. It implies that there is a significant relation of the two variables.

4.4 Correlation between Active Engagement and Student Experience

		Active Student Engagement	Student Experience
Active Student Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	.600**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Student Experience	Pearson Correlation	.600**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This correlation shows the relationship between perception on branding and employability and satisfaction. It yields a positive correlation coefficient (N) =100 it shows that there is exist a positive significant relationship between this two

variables is low and p-value of 0.000. The relationship significant is since p-value is 0.009 (level of significant). Hence, we Accept H2. It implies that there is a significant relation of the two variables.

4.5 Summary of Findings

Table 4.4.1., 4.4.2.and 4.4.3 this is the summary result of direct effect in the main model. The results answer Objectives. The summary can be used for further discussion in Chapter 5.

Hypothesis	Relationships	Decision
H1.	Student perception of the pre-enrolment has a positive impact on student.	Supported
H2.	Student active engagement at the university has a positive impact on student experience.	Supported
H3.	Student employability perception and satisfaction has a positive impact student experience.	Supported

4.6 Summary of the chapter

This chapter presents the results of analyzing data collected from survey. Response rate for the study is 70.0%. The data was analyzed using various statistical analysis techniques including descriptive analysis, factor analysis, reliability test, bivariate correlation, and regression analysis.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The survey results were presented in the last chapter. In this chapter, the justifications of those survey results are presented based on the comparison to existing literature. In addition, the implication and findings and research limitations of the study are discussed in this chapter. In the end, the conclusion of entire study is present, and highly helpful recommendation will be included for the university.

5.1 Implication of the Findings

The findings of this study will contribute directly to the Malaysian education academic sector. For the academic point, the result of the study will increase the knowledge on the impact of student experience as a tool that can add to student education. For the higher education, findings of the study will help educators to have a better way to evaluate their student or university and know the areas needed to be concern in other to improve the university.

5.2 Research Limitations

There are limitations in this research work, in this sense that not all perspectives were considered here as influence of higher education beyond branding, hence future improvement can include that in the research. This research work is also for the most part limited on local and international student experience in Malaysia, and the future improvement ought to consolidate other industrial segment in the research.

5.3 Recommendation for Future Study

Although, this research provided considerable results, several recommendations are proposed for the future studies in the similar areas of knowledge. In this research, Limkokwing University of Creative Technology related respondents were considered solely. The future studies can fulfill this particular area of knowledge. In addition, the existing literature review for this research limits the predictor of performance to five factors solely. The future study, can be conducted to delimit several other factor such as satisfaction, attitude etc., for much precise and comparative outcomes.

5.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, having analyzed the aim of this research work which entails study the factors affecting student experience in higher education beyond branding and also to ascertain at what level the higher education beyond branding on the student experience attempt by the institution as a factor towards high education.

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Therefore the practical value as led by this survey work is that in a growing corporate environment, there are huge importance for higher educational reviews to be sustained as this help the leaning institutions such as educational branding strategies that can and will keep the students motivated.

Another major breakthrough that was discovered in the research is the active engagement of student, employability perception and satisfaction. It also was uncovered that complimentary remarks/ words of encouragement or promotion was a vital motivator for student , as they were very determined to desert the institution if they do not foresee it coming. Some other huge rationale that were pondered as inducing the research outcomes were student simplification, culture etc.

DECLARATION

I declare that this project paper consists of my original work. The exception of quotation and citations which are duly acknowledged and that it has not been previously accepted for a degree and is not being concurrently considered for my other degree at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology or any institution.

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